

E-SERVICES AND PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM AS TOOLS TO ENHANCE SERVICE DELIVERY IN THE SOUTH AFRICAN POST OFFICE IN THE WATERBERG DISTRICT: A CASE OF THE LIMPOPO PROVINCE, SOUTH AFRICA

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Abstract

This paper argues that manual postal services are increasingly challenging for many postal administrators. Data show that, around the world, Post Offices are experiencing a significant decline in mail volume and profit margins. In the fiscal year 2023–2024, the South African Post Office reported a decrease in revenue and an operating loss of 139 million. Statistics indicate that if the digitization of postal services is not properly implemented, it could lead to a crisis for this organization. To boost revenue in the Waterberg district, the paper suggests ways to maximize income by transitioning from manual to electronic services. This article is based on a study conducted at the South African Post Office in the Waterberg district, located in Limpopo province of South Africa. Although SAPO plans to convert most manual transactions to e-services as a strategy to improve performance, this strategy has proven ineffective, as the organization continues to lose revenue. These challenges highlight the need for effective implementation of e-services. The study found that e-services positively impact service delivery and productivity at the South African Post Office. To enhance service delivery, the study recommends prioritizing the digitization of postal services to restore stability and promote the sustainability of the struggling South African Post Office. The research employed a mixed-methods approach: a questionnaire was used for quantitative data, and semi-structured interviews for qualitative insights. Systematic sampling was used to select customers, while purposive sampling was employed to select employees. Most respondents strongly agreed that e-services are vital for improving organizational performance. The article concludes with suggestions for the proper implementation of e-services. The findings will also benefit other organizations beyond the Waterberg district and Limpopo province postal branches.

Keywords: E-services, Digitization, Performance Management System, and Service Delivery.

1. Introduction

Post Office performances around the globe have been halted by traditional methods of rendering services to its customers. This has been proven by the fact that the Post Office had not modernised its operations using technology (Ittmann, 2023). Technology is largely believed to help Post Offices improve their financial position through the digitization of postal services. The digitization and modernization of South African Post Office products and services should be seen as a strategic imperative to improve the postal service (South African Post Office Annual Report, 2023:31).

According to Eposi (2021), research has proven that the introduction of technology by organizations has improved the quality of service and customer satisfaction has increased (Idrus, 2025:225). Ittmann (2023) correctly argued that the impact of modern technology and digitization has had a major impact on postal services around the world. This suggests that, being technologically inclined, management should reskill their employees to be in line with the current technological changes. In my opinion, digitization should apply to all state-owned enterprises, including the South African Post Office, to enhance service delivery. Because the postal service is not digitized, the entity is experiencing a huge decline in mail and a drop in financial revenues (SAPO Corporate Plan, 2024). Therefore, digitization from the Post Office context means the use of technology to coordinate resources and enhance financial performance, as well as an increasing mail volume. If the performance of postal operators is not up to standard, competitors will enter the postal market (Ittmann, 2023).

2. Problem Statement

The Post Offices in Waterberg have consistently shown a decrease in revenue growth. If this problem of low revenue growth is not addressed, it could lead to a catastrophic situation resulting in the closure of the postal business (Xiphu, 2014; Eposi, 2021; South African Post Office Corporate Plan, 2024). Waterberg postal branches

could collapse if these outlets become insolvent. The problem is that although the South African Post Office limitedly offers e-services, the company reliably shows a serious drop in revenue due to services that are not digitized. The Post Office suffered a net loss of R2.5 billion in the 2020–2021 fiscal year, a loss of R1.5 billion in the 2021–2022 fiscal year, and an operating loss of R561 million in the 2022–2023 fiscal year, according to SAPO national revenue performance statistics derived from the South African Post Office Corporate Plan (2024:48). The low revenue has further contributed to the nonpayment of critical creditors and outstanding liabilities, which amounted to R9.5 billion with statutory payment of R2.4 billion (South African Post Office Annual Report, 2023).

3. Literature Review

3.1 Legislative Frameworks

3.1.1 Postal Services Act (124 of 1998)

The South African Post Office is designated as the Republic of South Africa's universal postal service by the Postal Services Act (124 of 1998). By providing an acceptable level of efficient and regular postal services to all areas, including rural and small towns where Post Offices are not sustainable, Section 2 of the Act requires the Post Office to promote the universal and affordable provision of postal services, promote the development of postal services that are responsive to users' and consumers' needs, protect the interests of postal users and consumers, and ensure greater access to basic services. Additionally, it must ensure compliance with international commitments. Without a performance management system in place, the Post Office may find it challenging to deliver exceptional service. The Postal Services Act (124 of 1998) set the foundation for the performance management system of the South African Post Office, claims Eposi (2021).

3.1.2 South African Post Office SOC Act (22 of 2011)

The South African Post Office was established to serve the nation's population by providing postal services (Balkaran, 2015; Eposi, 2021). According to Section 2 of the Act, among other things, the Post Office must guarantee the provision of a broad range of postal services for the benefit of the Republic's economic development and growth, promote the growth of human resources and capacity building within the postal sector, and guarantee the provision of universal, accessible, dependable, and reasonably priced postal services.

To achieve all of this, as stated in Section 6(1), the Post Office must, by a date set by the Minister, annually enter into a performance agreement with the Minister to evaluate the Post Office's performance in the following year. Additionally, the Post Office must give copies of this performance agreement to the Minister.

The Act emphasizes the Performance Management System's vital significance in the postal industry and establishes the foundation for the South African Post Office's adoption of the system.

4. Theoretical Framework

The study adopted expectancy theory, and it is discussed in detail as follows:

4.1 Expectancy theory

Expectancy theory has proven to be a motivational strategy to make an employee take more decisive actions about the job (Ogundare and Omotosho, 2022:6). Likewise, Kumar and Prabhakar (2018:175) postulated that expectancy theory is an old concept but still occupies a predominant place in human resource administration, particularly motivating employees. The expectation theory of Vroom (1964) is based on the hypothesis that individuals adjust their behaviour in the organization based on anticipated satisfaction (Kumar and Prabhakar, 2018). According to theory, people choose to put their effort into activities they believe they can perform that will produce desired outcomes (DeSimone and Werner: 2012:49). Similarly, Ogundare and Omotosho (2022:1) suggest that the employee will be motivated to take some additional action if the value he or she places on the anticipated reward will ultimately meet its goal.

Expectancy theory suggests that there are three variables which motivate employees to perform which is (1) confidence in their ability to accomplish a task, (2) confirmation that there will be a reward for completing the task, and (3) the reward will be worth their effort (Lussier and Achan in Scott, 2018:3). Likewise, Kumar and Prabhakar (2018:175) confirmed that expectancy theory requires the availability of three factors which is valence, expectancy, and instrumentability. Kumar and Prabhakar (2018:175) further wrote that at some stage that the theory revolves around three elements, which are valence, expectancy, and instrumentability (Ogundare and Omotosho, 2022:5). This theory is supported by Kalogiannidis, Kalfas, Chalaris, Spinthiropoulos and Chatzitheodoridis (2025:238), who remarked that motivation is a function of three components: namely, perceived expectancy, perceived instrumentality, and perceived valence. According to this theory, employee motivation is undoubtedly centered on aligning incentives with output (Kumar and Prabhakar, 2018:175). The following is a discussion of the three factors:

4.1.1 Expectancy

The first component, 'expectancy', concerns what an employee expects after completing the work. Baumann and Bonner (2017) contended that expectancy is when an employee checks if their successful execution of work will lead to the intended outcome. According to Robbins and Judge (2019:264) expectancy refers to the possibility that the employee believes that an effort will lead to performance. Similarly, Chang and Jang (2008:314) concur with Robbins and Judge (2019) and refer to expectancy as the perceived probability that effort will lead to good performance. Ogundare and Omotosho (2022:5) affirmed that expectancy is the attitude of the employee by which he or she bases his journey towards performance. Kalogiandis et al., (2025: 238) wrote that at some stage that an individual will work hard to achieve high performance if he/she is convinced that expectancy, a high level of performance, will be rewarded. Employees expect a reward for the successful completion of work, and when a reward is absent, employees may not feel eager to perform to maximum levels.

4.1.2 Valence

The second component, 'valence', deals with the value of the reward after the successful completion of the assigned work. Baumann and Bonner (2017) explained that valence is whether the outcome is worth the behaviour. Ogundare and Omotosho (2022:5) refer to valence as the amount of value placed on the reward towards the individual goals. When a reward follows the behaviour, the individual is more likely to repeat the behaviour (Denhardt and Denhardt, 2009:342; Hellriegel et al.; 2012:421) Kalogiandis et al., (2025), emphasized that valence is the perceived worth of the outcome or reward to the individuals. Chiang and Jang (2018:314) also referred to valence as the value the individual personally places on rewards. Decision-makers are influenced by organizational compensation systems, which advise them on the best options based on their financial gain (Robbins, Judge, and Roodt, 2009:129).

Robbins and Judge (2019:264) regard valence as the extent to which the reward satisfies an individual's needs. Based on the expectancy theory, which highlights the significance of performance and reward, the study's goal concerning the first objective is to determine how well a performance management system has been implemented in the South African Post Office's Waterberg district in terms of service delivery. In my view, valence refers not only to a reward but also to the value that the reward has for the employee. Armstrong (2010:267 268) states that rewards are intended to help define what is important in terms of behaviours and outcomes, reward people based on the value they create, help attract and retain high-quality individuals the organization needs, and win the engagement of people.

4.1.3 Instrumentability

The third factor in expectancy theory is instrumentability. Baumann and Bonner (2017) have concluded that instrumentality is the impact the behaviour will have on achieving the outcome and the effort placed in achieving the goal. Ogundare and Omotosho (2022:5) proposed that instrumentability is performance aimed towards an outcome that will bring about the desired reward (Armstrong, 2012). Likewise, Chiang and Jang (2008: 314) regard instrumentability as the belief that if an individual meets performance expectations, he or she will receive a greater reward. Robbins and Judge (2019:264) regard instrumentability as the degree to which an employee believes efforts will lead to the attainment of a goal. One advantage of the theory is that it enables employers to recognize excellent performance (Ogundare and Omotosho, 2022:8).

It is in this context that Quratul in Kumar and Prabhakar (2018:176) believed that employee motivation and organizational effectiveness possess an optimistic relationship, and well-liked employees would produce better outcomes.

The above means that employees modify their behaviour to have an impact on the achievement of goals with the belief that they will be rewarded. The extent to which an individual is motivated to achieve a particular objective is related to the extent to which they believe that its achievement will result in desired results or reward (Wilton,2013:175). Aguinis (2013: 15) correctly argues that the performance management system rewards behaviours consistent with the attainment of organizational goals.

4.3.4 The Relationship between Expectancy, Valence, and Instrumentability

According to Chiang and Jang (2008:313), three different perceptions, expectancy, instrumentability, and valence, determine the driving force behind a behaviour, activity, or task. Expectancy theory argues that the strength of a tendency to act in a certain way depends on the strength of an expectation that the act will be followed by a given outcome, on the attractiveness of that outcome to the individual (Robbins et al.; 2009:157). Expectancy theory further proposes that employees will be motivated to exert a high level of effort when they believe that effort will lead to a good performance appraisal; that a good appraisal will lead to organizational rewards such as bonuses, salary increases, or promotions; and that the rewards will satisfy the employees' personal goals (Robbins et al., 2009:157).

The theory suggests that employees will be motivated to put more into their work only when they believe that the effort exerted will lead to a reward and the reward will have value. Inversely, employees will put less effort if they anticipate that their effort will not be rewarded. DeSimone and Werner (2012:40) correctly argue that if outcomes are not as rewarding as anticipated, the employees may revise their judgment about the value of such outcomes and perform different behaviours or leave the organization. With the three factors, which are expectancy, valence, and instrumentability, MaCkay (2007:103) confirmed that employees must believe that their efforts (expectancy) have a good chance (value) of producing the desired performance (instrumentability) (Kalogiannidis, 2025). DeSimone and Werner (2012:40) wrote at some stage that the relationship of the three elements means that if employees fulfil certain obligations to an organization but do not receive promised outcomes (such as promotions or pay raises), they may reduce their expectations about the link between their performance and the desired outcomes and thus choose to behave differently. Certo and Certo (2014:406) point out that the behaviour that is rewarded tends to be repeated. These three factors may mean that employees will increase their effort to achieve goals only when they are confident that their effort will be rewarded.

4.3.5 E-services and digitization of postal services

Moran et al., (2024: 1) refer to digitization as a process of utilizing digital technologies to optimize various aspects of business. According to the SAPO Corporate Plan (2024:30), digital and electronic services enable individuals and businesses to identify themselves legally with government certified digital identities (SAPO Corporate Plan, 2024: 30). Internet services will be available as part of South African Post Office service offerings and will include emailing, web browsing, website design and hosting, and e-government services (SAPO Corporate Plan, 2024:32).

Since digitization is thought to be a solution to some organizational issues, management should use creativity to make sure it is implemented effectively to meet the organization's objectives (Eposi, 2021:52). Likewise, Salamzadeh, Rahim and Salamzadeh (2022:640) confirmed that digitization is a cyclic process involving rethinking, redesigning, retooling, and analysing workflows and business process within an organization (Junior and Kamienski, 2021). (Jayadi, 2024:8) alerted us that digitization is an emerging concept and relatively new (Ittamann, 2023). Hassel and Sieker, as cited in Samambet and Khouaangvichit (2025:3), affirmed that the growth of online business has increased rivalry in the delivery industry, as organizations strive to become dominant by using technology such as digitalization and sophisticated tracking systems to improve efficiency and prioritize client satisfaction. Likewise, Dessler (2013:32) remarked that efficiency improves performance and increases profit.

4.4 Benefits of e-services services

According to Maleka (2016:171), the benefits of e-services are improved government decision-making, increased citizen trust in government, increased accountability, and the ability to accommodate the needs of the public (Dessler, 2013). Idrus (2025:226) affirmed that one of the most significant benefits of technology is its ability to provide data-driven insights. The benefits of digitization are discussed below as follows:

4.4.1 Enhancing customer service

Through e-services, public service customers could be in a better position to influence policy and improve service delivery (Maleka, 2016:168). The Post Office mail delivery division will improve the delivery cycle time of parcel deliveries and improve the tracking of customer shipments from the origin to the final delivery (SAPO Corporate Plan, 2024:36). Diallo et al., in Samambet and Khouaangvichit (2025:13) supported the assertion that technology also helped in customs clearance as well as monitor the parcel along the shipment route. According to the customer's consideration, the long waiting time for the service creates a negative impact on the customer's perception about the service (Eposi, 2021:56; Puspitasari and Sutianingsih, 2025:617). Digitizing core business processes improves productivity, quality, and customer satisfaction by delivering more value to the customer (Hameed et al., 2022:638). Quinlan et al., (2019: 292) affirmed that organizations have adopted a total quality management philosophy and believe that focus should be directed to customers. These technologies not only increased the efficiency and precision of postal services but also increased the overall consumer satisfaction (Samambet and Khouaangvichit, 2025:3).

Similarly, Bakar et al., (2020:82) affirmed the benefit of digitization for customers as a wider access to services and information regarding transactions made. The South African Post Office should notify the customer of all payments or fund transfer transactions above a specified value (South African Post Office Information Policy, 2023:32). With digitization and increasing global connectivity, e-Commerce gives customers access to markets all over the world (Ittamann, 2023). It appears that not all customers are comfortable with digital platforms; the aged are more averse to digital technologies than the youth, and thus closing the digital divide is difficult (Samambet and Khouaangvichit, 2025). This may suggest that customers are part of the core business of the organization,

and the Post Office should be aware that without customers the entity will collapse, and the institution should be flexible to the technological needs of the customers.

4.4. 2 Global connectivity

Prabhu in Maleka (2016:169) showed that digitization has found expression in developing countries, enhancing the relationship between entities and their citizens (Ittmann, 2023). On a global platform, the South African Post Office intends to enhance the visibility of the Post Office brand on the digital platform (SAPO Corporate Plan, 2024:44).

Eposi (2021:175) wrote at some stage that South African Post Office IT systems are unstable, without adequate connectivity, weak redundancy, without disaster recovery, and are certain to collapse in the immediate future if no drastic and urgent intervention is taken; system failures could lead to excessive inefficiencies, losses, and waste. Bakar et al., (2020:78) showed that the globe is in the mode of the fourth Industrial Revolution, where people need the cyber world and technology to operate. Likewise, Mahlangu and Schutte (2024:1) remarked that entities worldwide should implement extreme measures to modernize service provision and increase the performance of the organization. India is also amongst countries focusing on digitization to participate in the international economy (Mello, 2015: 248). Moran et al., (2024: 2) also remarked that digitization is advancing globally, and the European Union has introduced the digital intensity index as a key performance indicator that highlights Europe's ambitious vision of digital transformation.

According to the South African Post Office Annual Report (2023:45), the participation of the South African Post Office within international space is guided by the framework of the Government's White Paper on international relations (Ittamann, 2023). Eposi (2021:142) correctly argued that the fall in the patronage of postal services in many societies across the world could be attributed to the emergence of the Internet as a strong competitive force in the global and South African postal sector. Global connectivity may be beneficial because technology connects the South African Post Office with the global market, which has the potential to maximize revenue growth.

4.4.3 Increased profitability and productivity

Many businesses lack adequate financial resources in a business climate that is changing quickly; consequently, digitization could result in higher production and better profit (Ulrich-Diener, Dvoulety, and Spacek, 2025). The main reason for restructuring entities is to increase revenue and to increase efficiency (Umar and Balewa, 2023). Ulrich-Dener et al., (2025) wrote that growth performance can be compared from revenue and net profit to the use of existing and acquired resources (Bakar et al., 2020; Ittamann, 2023). The South African Post Office management needs to focus on high product quality to influence both profitability and market share growth (Eposi, 2021: 176).

The South African Post Office Information Technology is still dedicated to spearheading the strategic initiatives to establish effective systems and procedures to enhance Post Office market relevance through digital transformation, as stated in the South African Post Office Annual Report (2023:39) (Anindya and Irawan, 2025:157; Puspitasari and Sutianingsih, 2025:606). The advantage is that with digitization, employees can work remotely, and organizations save on rented buildings (Bakar et al., 2020:79). Likewise, Mello (2015:252) confirmed that digitization has a positive impact on productivity, quality of product, delivery output, cost of equipment, and new market opportunities (SAPO Corporate Plan, 2024:15 and Natsir, Ramli and Putra, 2024). Productivity requires effectiveness and efficiency (Robbins and Judge, 2019:63). Digitization has also improved business productivity and customer satisfaction (Samambet and Khouaangvichit, 2025). The statement is in line with Puspitasari and Sutianingsih (2025:606), who remarked that by increasing productivity, companies can optimize the use of resources, increase efficiency, and ultimately achieve the goals that have been set (Darmawan, 2024:49). It is against this background that digitization could have a positive influence on profit margins and productivity levels. However, it requires efficient and effective employees to increase production, complemented by automation.

4.4.4 Enhanced security

The digital workplace also gives freedom and control for both employees and Information Technology by creating an agile and secure workplace and the built-in security features, which offers robust employee identity and devise management (Bakar et al., 2020:82). Opara and Soluade in Mahlangu and Schutte (2024:1) warned of potential threats and untrusted networks due to cyber security attacks (Junior and Kamienski, 2021:97). With employees working remotely, there is an inherent risk of human error that IT departments were unaware of, and the vulnerability of employees to security measures is enhanced (Mahlangu and Schutte, 2024:2). Supporting Mahlangu and Schutte (2024), Idrus (2025:226) affirmed that reliance on technology introduces challenges, particularly to data security and privacy. Concerns over job stability and working conditions have emerged due to

the possibility of restructuring in a privatized setting to enhance performance (Strule in Samambet and Khouaangvichit, 2025:25). According to the South African Post Office Information Technology Policy (2023:31) the South African Post Office needs to report all cyber security incidents including spasm, email phishing, whaling, fishing fraud to the South African Police Service. To build confidence and prevent attacks, customer data and digital transactions need strong security (Adriano in Samambet and Khouaangvichit, 2025:25). Ryan in Mahlangu and Schutte (2024:1) affirmed that 44% of employees have experienced incidents of hacking, phishing, and cyber fraud due to poor security procedures and security training of employees.

South African Post Office Annual Report (2023:42) reported that there has been a notable increase in security-related incidents and an increase in the reported loss amounting to R42.4 million, with fraud taking the lead with R88.0 million. Security Information Technology aims to improve the company's IT infrastructure and systems to support efficient and effective internal processes, including the application of advanced technologies such as automation, artificial intelligence to improve data management, decision making, and operational efficiency (Anindya and Irawan, 2025:157).

South African Post Office Information Technology Policy (2023) explained that physical access to SAPO information systems facilities should be restricted to authorized persons only to avoid unlawful activities. Additionally, the South African Post Office Information Policy (2023: 25) states that appropriate controls should be designed based on security requirements and risk assessment that have an impact on sensitive and critical information, and that operational databases containing personal information or any other sensitive information should not be used for testing purposes. SAPO corporate plan (2024:25) affirmed that all revenue lines have continued to decline, exacerbated by the lack of technology and infrastructure investment, the lack of tools of trade, and compounded by an unsustainable cost base. Applied to the postal context, it may mean that managers should be aware of the crimes that come with technology (cybercrime) and stop that crime before it occurs through strong security systems.

5. Method

Crotty in Cheek and Oby (2023:12) outlined how the strategy, plan of action, process, or design that underpins the selection and application of methodologies and connects them to the intended result is known as research methodology.

Lancaster (2005:78) referred to research methodology as the general approach used in a research or consultancy study, which relates particularly to the approach to data collection. In this article, a mixed-method approach was used. These two methodological approaches aimed to understand the impact of e-services in the South African Post Office, Waterberg district, Limpopo province. To probe some aspects pertaining to the research questions and research objectives, a semi-structured interview was conducted with the Waterberg district Manager, trade union representatives, and Post Office customers.

For quantitative data, questionnaires were distributed to Post Office employees, Branch Managers, Managers, Tellers, supervisors, and Human Resources Practitioners. A 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree " to strongly agree with "undecided" as a neutral point was used to solicit data from the respondents.

6. Findings and Discussion

The results and discussion in this article are based on two variables, which are E-services and digital re-skilling. The results are presented individually as follows:

6.1 E-services

This variable emerged whilst probing whether the E-services improve the performance of the Post Office. Among its functions, the Post Office renews vehicle licenses, accepts deposits and transactions entered in smart save books, as well as remittance of cash to third parties. These transactions necessitate these services be conducted electronically. It is against this backdrop that there was a necessity to probe whether postal services should be electronically transacted. The respondents in this study area indicated as follows:

6.2 E-services Improve the Performance of the Post Office

1. E-Services Improve the Performance of the Post Office					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	6	7,6	7,6	7,6

Disagree	13	16,5	16,5	24,1
Undecided	8	10,1	10,1	34,2
Agree	25	31,6	31,6	65,8
Strongly Agree	27	34,2	34,2	100,0
Total	79	100,0	100,0	

This table presents the opinions of the 79 employees regarding whether the digitization of postal services improves the overall performance of the Post Office. All 79 respondents provided valid answers to this question.

A clear majority of employees believe that digitization **does** improve performance:

- **27 individuals Strongly Agreed** with the statement, representing **34.2%** of the sample.
- **25 individuals Agreed**, representing **31.6%** of the sample.

Combined, **65.8%** of the employees hold a positive view regarding the impact of digitization on the Post Office's performance. Darmawan (2024) articulated that e-services increases productivity and efficiency, and companies can achieve goals that had been projected.

A smaller portion expressed negative views:

- **13 individuals Disagreed**, representing **16.5%** of the sample.
- **6 individuals Strongly Disagreed**, representing **7.6%** of the sample.

Finally, **8 individuals** were **Undecided**, representing **10.1%** of the sample.

In summary, the data indicates a consensus among employees that the digitization of postal services is having a positive impact on the performance of the Post Office. This suggests that these technological advancements are perceived as beneficial for the organization's efficiency and effectiveness.

The graphic representation below responds to the variable of whether e-services improve the performance of the Post Office

Identification of training needs

The second variable was posed to determine whether Electronic Performance Management System identifies training needs and the responses are tabulated below as follows:

7. Electronic Performance Management System Assists Managers in Identifying Training Needs

Electronic Performance Management System Assists Managers in Identifying Training Needs

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	10,1	10,1	10,1
	Disagree	17	21,5	21,5	31,6
	Undecided	13	16,5	16,5	48,1
	Agree	32	40,5	40,5	88,6
	Strongly Agree	9	11,4	11,4	100,0
	Total	79	100,0	100,0	

This table presents the responses of the 79 employees regarding whether the electronic Performance Management System (EPMS) assists managers in identifying training needs within the South African Post Office. All 79 respondents provided valid answers to this question.

A clear majority of employees believe that the EPMS **does** assist managers in identifying training needs:

- **32 individuals Agreed** with the statement, representing **40.5%** of the sample.
- **9 individuals Strongly Agreed**, representing **11.4%** of the sample.

Combined, **51.9%** of the employees hold a positive view regarding the electronic Performance Management System's role in identifying training requirements. According to Amos, Ristow and Ristow (2019:328), the starting point for any training or development process is to check performance management database to identify the reason or need for it. This means that the electronic Performance Management System significantly supports management in identifying training needs.

A notable portion of employees expressed uncertainty or disagreement:

- **13 individuals were Undecided**, representing **16.5%** of the sample.
- **17 individuals Disagreed**, representing **21.5%** of the sample.
- **8 individuals Strongly Disagreed**, representing **10.1%** of the sample.

Combined, **48.1%** of the employees are either unsure or do not believe the PMS effectively assists managers in identifying training needs.

In summary, while a slight majority of employees perceive the EPMS as helpful in identifying training needs, a significant proportion either disagree or are uncertain. This suggests that while the system may have some positive impact in this area, there is also room for improvement or a lack of clear understanding among a considerable segment of the workforce. The graphic representation below responds to the variable whether electronic. Performance Management System assists managers in identifying training needs.

The Electronic Performance Management System assists managers in identifying training needs

7. Recommendations

It is against this background that the following recommendations were made:

7.1 Converting manual services into e-services

Emanating from the findings of the study, it was revealed that Post Offices in the Waterberg district are not in line with the current technological setup. Most transactions are still being performed manually and are time-consuming for both Post Office employees and its customers. We are living in a technological world where customers prefer to conduct business in the comfort of their own space. Furthermore, manual services attract higher labour costs as opposed to technology that is cheaper efficient with less labour. Conversion of manual services to e-services also reduces human errors that could become expensive to rectify. Basically, modernization of postal services will bring about high revenue, fewer faults performed by employees, more convenient services to clients, and less management intervention in overseeing the operations of the postal branch. E-services put the Post Office in a position to compete with other companies offering the same services as the Post Office does. Holding back traditional services will close many opportunities for the Post Office, and the postal service will ultimately be non-existent. It is therefore recommended that Post Office management consider automating, modernizing, and digitizing the postal service to be on par with other competitive industries offering the same service.

7.2 Identification of digital training needs

Emanating from the findings of the study, it was revealed that the electronic Performance Management System assists managers in the Post Offices in the Waterberg district to identify training needs of the employees. Once training needs are identified, managers should come up with a developmental plan to improve the capacity of employees to perform digital functions. Mello and Makamu (2021:648) have concluded that organizations that identify their employees' digital needs are likely to achieve their goals, and skilling becomes paramount. That is, failure to adapt to the new digital practices could lead to an increased loss to the organization. A fully digitalized operational system forces employees and managers to have a digital mindset, and this could be achieved through training. The introduction of technology necessitates the re-skilling of staff members to be in line with technological developments. Training and awareness are a crucial pillar that enables Information and Technology users to adapt to new technological developments (Mahlangu and Schutte, 2024).

8. Conclusions

The study has proven that digitization and modernization of postal services are a practical strategy to increase profit margins and improve service delivery at the South African Post Office. Based on the preceding discussion, it was noted that the benefit of digitization includes improved customer service, increased productivity, and water-tight security. Global connectivity is another area that the Post Office management should seriously consider to increase profit margins.

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